

INDIVIDUALISED HOMOEOPATHIC TREATMENT OF A FILIFORM WART: A CASE STUDY

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ABSTRACT

Non-genital warts are most common, benign skin disease in daily clinical practice. This disease has cosmetic and psychological impact in daily life. Homoeopathy offers a salutary treatment for the removal of warts almost permanently by internal medication only. This is a case of 12 year boy having filiform wart over the back of the neck. Individualised homoeopathic medicine Antimonium Crudum 200 was prescribed and in one and half month wart has been completely disappeared without any use of local treatment.

KEYWORDS: Wart, Homoeopathy, Antimonium Crudum.

INTRODUCTION

Non-genital warts (verrucae) are an extremely common, benign and usually a self-limited skin disease. Infection of epidermal cells with the human papilloma virus (HPV) results in cell proliferation and a thickened, warty papule on the skin. There are over 100 different types of HPV. The appearance of warts is determined by the type of virus and the location of the infection.^[1] External genital warts (EGWs) are sexually transmitted benign epidermal growths caused by the human papilloma virus (HPV), on the anogenital areas of both females and males.^[2] Non-genital warts are divided into subtypes; common, palmo-plantar, plane, mosaic and Filiform. Morphologically, these comprised common (42%), palmo-plantar (20%), plane (18%), mosaic (6%), and Filiform/digitate (4%) types.^[3]

Risk of developing warts include; people who work with raw meat, children who often use communal showers or at the swimming pool, family members who have warts, persons with weakened immune system: especially adults and children who have had an organ transplant or who have a serious disease like cancer or AIDS, and people with atopic conditions like eczema.

Few precautions like not to share towels, shoes, gloves or socks, avoid touching and scratching the warts because after scratching virus might spread.^[4]

Various types of treatment procedures are available for removing warts. Some of these are (a) applying *salicylic acid*, *liquid nitrogen* and *podophyllin*; (b) loop

electrosurgical excision procedure; (c) CO₂ laser surgery; and (d) interferon injections.^[5]

Homoeopathy has a major role in the treatment of warts. Hahnemann the founder of Homoeopathy significantly described the character and nature of wart under sycosis.^[6] Several medicines according to site, type, Character of warts have been used and Homoeopathy offers only internal medication without using local treatment, so by this way it treats disease from within and permanently. There are many medicine as stated earlier but few most commonly used medicines for warts are Thuja, Causticum, Calcaria Carbonicum, Antimonium Crudum, Nitric acid, Sabina, Lycopodium clavatum etc.

Present case report of filiform wart is showing the positive effect of the homoeopathic medicine *Antimonium Crudum* in a short span of time. This case is an attempt to document the usefulness of homoeopathic treatment in the warts without using the local treatment. An increasing number of such cases will create an adequate database to enable a well designed research study in this area.

Presenting Concerns

A 12 year old boy, student, with chief complaint of an oval horny excrescence (7-8mm) of the skin over the back of the neck visited the O.P.D. dated on 29.08.2015. Patient has been suffering from this complaint since 2 years. Sometimes there was excessive itching with bleeding of the part.

History of present complaint

Wart gradually appeared 2 years back and increased in size over the period of time. No significant cause found associated with it.

Past History

Once patient suffered from Pneumonia at age of 2 years and from Jaundice at age of 8 year.

Family History

Father is suffering from Diabetes Mellitus, Grand Father and Grand Mother suffering from Hypertension and Diabetes Mellitus. No significant illness noted in mother.

Physical Generals

- Appetite: diminished appetite, loathing of food
- Taste: bitter taste of mouth
- Tongue: slightly white coated
- Desire: acidic food; vinegar, pickles
- Aversion: nothing
- Thirst: thirsty, feeling of dryness of lips
- Sweat: not significant
- Bowel: constipated, every day go for stool, hard, unsatisfactory. Anus excoriated
- Urine: Nothing significant

- Sleep: Regular refreshing
- Dreams: of quarrelling
- Worse: From Heat of Sun

Mental Generals

Shy nature, doesn't want to speak, Aversion to work, anxious and pain in stomach.

On Examination

There was solitary (7-8 mm in size), rough, sharply defined, horny, dry wart over the nape of the neck.

Repertorisation

Repertorisation of case has been done through from Hompath software (Figure-1) and the rubrics were taken as:-

- Skin: Warts: Horny
- Skin: Warts: Itching
- Stomach: Appetite: Diminished
- Mouth: Coated: White: Tongue
- Generalities: Food and drinks: Pickles: Desires
- Food: Aversion, to food (Loathing)
- Mind and disposition: Dreams: About quarrelling

Figure-1: Repertorisation sheet.

Table-1: Repertorisation Table.

Repertorisation Sheet - Hompath WildFire															
Physician Name : Dr. Ashish Kumar Dixit															
Patient Name : Mr. XX															
Reg. No. : -----															
Date : 21/01/2018															
Remedy	Ant-c	Sep	Sulph	Calc	Ars	Bry	Nit-ac	Arn	Chin	Cocc	Kali-c	Merc	Puls	Caust	Phos
Totality	18	18	15	11	11	11	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	9	9
Symptoms Covered	6	6	6	5	4	4	5	4	3	3	3	3	3	5	5
[Murphy] [Skin]Warts, skin, (see Condylomata or Excrescences): Horny:	3	2	2	2	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0
[Complete] [Skin]Warts, condylomata:Itching:	0	3	1	1	0	0	3	0	0	0	3	0	0	0	1
[Complete] [Stomach]Appetite: Diminished:	4	4	4	4	4	4	3	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4
[Complete] [Mouth] Coated: White: Tongue:	4	3	3	3	3	4	1	3	3	3	0	4	4	1	1
[Complete] [Generalities]Food and drinks: Pickles: Desires:	3	3	3	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
[Murphy] [Food]Aversion, to food, (see Loathing):	3	3	2	1	3	2	1	2	3	3	3	2	2	1	2
[Gentry] [Mind and disposition] Dreams: About quarrelling:	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1

Treatment

Antimonium Crudum 200/1 dose in sugar of milk was advised to take empty stomach early in the morning and placebo 4 pills of 40 no. size three times/ day for 7 days.

Follow-up, observation and Intervention

Table-2: Details of Follow-up visits, complaints and intervention.

S.No.	Follow-up Visits	Chief Complaints	Intervention
1	29/08/2015	Horny wart of 7-8 mm size, itching and bleeding sometimes	Antimonium Crudum 200/1dose Once empty stomach in morning with Placebo Three times/ day
2	04/09/2015	Wart starting to regress though not much reduced	Placebo; Three time/ day
3	13/09/2015	Much reduced, little roughness remains	Placebo; Three time/ day
4	14/10/2015	Smooth skin, Completely regress no remnants of wart present	No further medicine prescribed

Figure-2: Wart as on dated 29/08/15.

Figure-2: Wart as on dated 04/09/15.

Figure-2: Wart as on dated 13/09/15.

Figure-2: Wart as on dated 14/10/15.

DISCUSSION

In this case one of the subtypes of wart i.e. filiform wart has been studied. Case shows the importance of individuality in homeopathic prescribing. 12 years boy having this wart since two years though not bothersome (as most of the warts produce no marked complaint) but sometimes itching and on account of itching bleeding occurs. After thorough investigation and examination of case, where mental generals, physical generals and the peculiarity of local disease have been considered according to the fundamentals laid down in the Organon of Medicine.^[7] Case has been repertorised from the Homopath software after taking the important rubrics from the case (Figure-1). Repertorial result has shown Antimonium Crudum the top most homeopathic medicine, covering 6 rubrics out of 7 with 16 marks (Table-1). Sepia and Sulphur also covered 6 rubrics but the other important symptoms are not under these medicines like horny wart is lesser degree in both these medicines and white coating of the tongue which is very important symptoms for the prescribing of Antimonium Crudum^[8] and graded as in double thick line in Hering Guiding symptoms.^[9] Another very important symptom of the case was the desire for pickles though covered by all the top three drugs; Antimonium Crudum, Sepia and Sulphur but this peculiar desire has been stressed by most of the authors pertaining to Antimonium Crudum in our source book as in single thick line by Hering Guiding symptoms and in italics in Boericke's Materia Medica.^[10] Finally considering all the facts and consulting with Materia Medica books, Antimonium Crudum in potency 200 has been selected for the case and advised to take 1

dose of this medicine empty stomach early in the morning with Placebo 4 pills three times in day for seven days (Table-2) with follow-up at every 7 days. On the first visit photograph has been taken Figure-2. On the second visit, warts starting to reduced but not much as mention in Table-2, Figure-3. On subsequent visits marked improvement has been seen (Figure-4 and Figure-5). During the whole course of treatment no use of any kind of local treatment advised.

CONCLUSION

Present case highlights the effectiveness of internal medication of individualized homeopathic medicine in the treatment of warts. However, the results from this single case report are by no means conclusive regarding the long-term clinical effectiveness of homeopathy for warts. Well designed studies are required for establishing effectiveness and efficacy of homeopathy in treating these conditions.

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